

D6.3: Communication toolkit

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

D6.3: Communication Toolkit

Due date:

31/07/2020

Actual submission date:

12/07/2021

Project start date:

01/01/2020

Duration:

36 months

Work Package concerned:

WP6: Sharing results and multiplying impacts.

Concerned work package leader:

AEIDL

Dissemination level:

PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Revision history:

Version 1.0: final version submitted on 31/07/2020.

Version 1.1: revised version submitted on 12/07/2021 implementing modifications requested during the first project review process.

Disclaimer

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1. Introduction

The communication toolkit produced by BEpart aims to be used extensively during dissemination activities of the TRANSFORM project by all project partners and the network involved at European level and clusters levels. It includes communication templates (document templates in Word format and presentation layout in Power Point format), communication tools (web banners, logos and videos) and a section dedicated to the design of a project brochure that will be finalised in concertation with WP leaders and Clusters partners. All communication materials are adaptable to local needs and languages.

The communication toolkit is a living document that will evolve over the course of the project to adapt to TRANSFORM needs at different phases of the project lifetime. This document includes the main communication tools useful at M7, the due date for this deliverable. It will evolve, until the end of the project with a first milestone being the issue of the project brochure in the last quarter of 2020.

2. Templates

The communication toolkit includes two templates for the documents produced by the project (in Word format) and one for presentations (Power Point format).

2.1 Documents templates

2.1.1 Simple document

Figure 1. Simple document template

2.1.2 Simple document with letterhead

Figure 2. Simple document template with letterhead

2.1 Presentation template

The communication toolkit provides a template to be used for all presentations related to the TRANSFORM project in Power Point format. A screenshot of this template is available in Figure 3 and an extract of the template in Annex 1.

Figure 3. Screenshot of TRANSFORM presentation template in Power point

3. Banners

3.1 Website

The website banner has been designed for the communication on the project website and other websites disseminating results and multiplying TRANSFORM's impacts (partners portals and other relevant websites).

Figure 4. TRANSFORM project website banner 1

In addition, an animated banner is available to provide a dynamic image of the project on relevant websites. The animated banner is available here:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1PVzexJ7c10rB2n75UoKHNXu65yJ64tuR/view?usp=sharing>

3.2 Twitter

The toolkit includes two banners and a profile picture to communicate about TRANSFORM on Twitter.

Figure 5. TRANSFORM project Twitter banner 1

TERRITORIES AS RESPONSIVE AND ACCOUNTABLE NETWORKS OF S3 THROUGH NEW FORMS OF OPEN AND RESPONSIBLE DECISION-MAKING

TRANSFORM

Figure 6. TRANSFORM project Twitter banner 2

Figure 7. TRANSFORM project Twitter profile icon

3.3 LinkedIn

The toolkit includes a banner and a profile picture to communicate about TRANSFORM to be used on LinkedIn.

Figure 8. TRANSFORM project LinkedIn banner

TRANSFORM

Figure 9. TRANSFORM project LinkedIn profile icon

4. Videos

Two short promotional videos are available to the project partners and actors from the TRANSFORM network to communicate about the project. It is a dynamic tool to instil the project visual identity.

The first video is available in portrait format, as can be seen in the Figure 10:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1VqOsHudqKRric58eq9U2mzPGLIVGmXs1/view?usp=sharing>

Figure 10. Screenshot TRANSFORM visual identity video 1 – portrait format

The second video is available in landscape format, as can be seen in the Figure 11:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1TJo4iQxtmBBYqr6m5NepRhoppaanLRY2p/view?usp=sharing>

Figure 11. Screenshot TRANSFORM visual identity video 2 – landscape format

5. Logos

5.1 General project logo

The communication toolkit includes the TRANSFORM logo in three versions: the symbol alone (see Figure 12), the symbol with the project name in square format (see Figure 13) and in horizontal format (see

Figure 14). These three logo versions are available in colours and in black and white.

Figure 12. TRANSFORM logo – symbol alone in black and white and in colours

Figure 13. TRANSFORM logo – symbol & project name (square) in black and white and in colours

Figure 14. TRANSFORM logo – symbol & project name (horizontal) in black and white and in colours

5.1 Clusters logos

The TRANSFORM project logo has four declinations of the main visual identity symbol in different shapes and colours for the three regional clusters and the international partner. For each of these declinations, a square and a horizontal format is available.

5.1.1 Catalonia cluster logos

Figure 15. Catalonia TRANSFORM cluster logos

5.1.2 Lombardy cluster logos

Figure 16. Lombardy TRANSFORM cluster logos

5.1.4 Brussels-Capital region cluster logos

Figure 17. Brussels-Capital Region TRANSFORM cluster logos

5.1.4 Boston international partner logos

Figure 18. Boston TRANSFORM international partner logos

6. Project brochure

The communication toolkit is a living document that will be adapted during the various stages of the project to answer the communication needs appearing with different milestones. The brochure is planned to be published in the last quarter of 2020 and will aim to communicate about the project to various target groups outside of the project consortium. It will be printed and available in electronic format, downloadable from the project website. The aim of this brochure is to target a large public and to communicate about the project with concise and engaging message, content accessible to a variety of publics, including those that are not expert in the project topics.

Two declinations of the project brochure will be available, one general version for dissemination at European level in English and several local ones in national languages for the three regional clusters and the international partner. The brochure will include five sections, the last one will be adapted to local needs:

1. **Heading:** Project title, logo, and full name
2. **What?** Project description in text and a chart that will describe the TRANSFORM project processes in an attractive visual way
3. **Who?** Some figures regarding the composition of the consortium and the clusters, highlighting the diversity of stakeholders involved in the project
4. **Why?** The main objectives of the project
5. **How?** Information on the main activities in clusters

The fifth section will be adapted according to the brochure versions. It will include information on how TRANSFORM is piloting concrete R&I methods in regional clusters. For the general European brochure, the section will include high-level information on the 3 clusters and the international partner with a similar space:

- Catalunya Cluster focus on Citizen Science,
- Lombardy Cluster work on participatory research agenda setting,
- Brussels-Capital Region activities on design for social innovation and
- Boston on the CC-PES project and pairing with EU regions

Then, each cluster will have a brochure in the language(s) of their region with additional information describing in detail the activities organised on their territory.

A draft of the general version of the brochure, that will be finalised and published in the last quarter of 2020 is presented in Figure 19:

TRANSFORM

TERRITORIES AS RESPONSIVE AND ACCOUNTABLE NETWORKS OF S3 THROUGH NEW FORMS OF OPEN AND RESPONSIBLE DECISION-MAKING

What?

- ❖ An H2020 EU-funded project (2020-2022) that brings together three European regions – **Lombardy** (Italy), **Brussels-Capital** (Belgium) and **Catalonia** (Spain), pairing with a co-creation initiative in **Boston** (USA).
- ❖ TRANSFORM connects two innovative policy concepts: **Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI)** and **Smart Specialisation Strategies (S3)**. **RRI** is an approach that aims at aligning research and innovation (R&I) with expectations, values and needs of society. **S3** focuses on the strengths and competitive advantages that territories like regions have, to encourage growth, jobs & prosperity through local partnerships.
- ❖ The main focus of TRANSFORM is to **strengthen RRI components of research & innovation policies at regional level**, by proposing and testing actions aimed at the long-term engagement of quadruple-helix stakeholders (business, research, civil society and public administration). In particular, TRANSFORM aims at strengthening the good and responsible governance of regional S3 priorities. The three regions involved will run pilot actions within their chosen local strategic priorities (e.g. smart mobility and green economy). The pilots are aimed at implementing interactive and inclusive processes that will make local R&I priorities more connected to societal needs, while generating more creative and socially acceptable solutions through the involvement of multiple stakeholders and contributing to the local public good.
- ❖ Each regional cluster involved in TRANSFORM – composed of public administrations and other actors such as universities and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) - will design, test and disseminate a **methodological framework** relevant to each local territory (research agenda setting in Lombardy, citizen science in Catalonia and design thinking for social innovation in Brussels-Capital). The impact of TRANSFORM pilot actions will be assessed, leading to concrete guidelines on how to implement RRI approaches within S3 R&I policies and showcasing added values emerging from it.

IMAGE

(To be drawn by hand, by the graphic designer. The chart should visually show the processes of the TRANSFORM project)

Who?

(logos of partners in state of names)

<h2><u>How?</u></h2> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ TRANSFORM project works in regional territories at institutional level and in the field with the objective to make R&I ecosystems more open, transparent, and democratic in Europe. The aim is to work with the networks of stakeholders involved in regional R&I, considering the political, economic, social, and cultural context in which R&I takes place to have an impact on regional innovation processes. ❖ Empower diverse stakeholders providing them guidelines, indicators, and tools to enable them to implement and/or engage with the development of responsible regional development processes and evaluate their impact. ❖ Explore concrete R&I working methods based on three sound methodological approaches: participatory research agenda setting, citizen science and design for social innovation. ❖ To advance RRI in territories, TRANSFORM extensively promotes the share of best practices, learnings, and the diffusion of governance innovations in the clusters of the project, and with the results from the project beyond in other regions of the European Union. 	<p>TRANSFORM pilots concrete R&I methods in regional clusters</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1090 383 1241 551"> BOSTON	Capacity building for Co-Created Public Engagement with Science (CC-PES)							
 BRUSSELS	Activities on <i>Design-thinking for Social Innovation</i>								
 CATALONIA	Actions on <i>Citizen Science</i>								
 LOMBARDY	Works on <i>Participatory Research Agenda Setting</i>								
 BOSTON	Capacity building for Co-Created Public Engagement with Science (CC-PES)								
<p>Follow us </p>									

Figure 19. Draft TRANSFORM brochure

7. Annexes

Annex 1 – Presentation template in Power Point format

TRANSFORM

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 TRANSFORM project group

 TRANSFORM project

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